

Research Article

Incidence of malaria among various rural socio-economic households

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ABSTRACT

It is shown from the literatures that malaria is a disease caused by a parasite that is transmitted by an *Anopheles* mosquito. The disease that is prevalent in the tropical or sub-tropical climates. In Nigeria, malaria causes the death of an estimated 250,000 children under the age of five every year. The study aimed at applying multi-linear regression method to analyse the socio-economic factors associated with malaria incidence among various socio-economic households in rural areas taking Akinyele local government as a case study. Using systematic and simple random sampling methods, 387 respondents are interviewed through the administration of structured questionnaire. Regression result shows a strong significant relationship between malaria incidence and socio-economic characteristics of respondents within the various households ($R=0.258$ at $P<0.05$). The regression model shows that household size $\beta=0.258$ at $p<0.05$ and religion $\beta=0.123$ at $p<0.05$ are the major significant factors influencing malaria incidence among the various rural socio-economic households. The study suggests the intensification of the teaching of family planning and health education, and the use of soap opera and staged play in local languages to disseminating essential information about malaria to the people.

Key words: anopheles, rural, households, malaria

BACKGROUND

Malaria is a disease caused by a parasite that is transmitted by an *Anopheles* mosquito. The symptoms include fever, chills, headaches, muscle aches and general malaise (similar to flu symptoms). This disease is prevalent in tropical or sub-tropical climates (Freudenrich, 2011). In Nigeria, malaria causes the deaths of an estimated 250,000 children under the age of five every year. Malaria is responsible for about 66 per cent of all clinic visits in Nigeria. Health workers are sometimes forced to work overtime, and doctors and nurses can be on duty for over 12 hours a day (UNICEF/Nigeria/2009/).

There have been several efforts, policies, programs across several countries of the globe in order to find the best method or combination of methods for control of malaria and other related social and environmental factors that influence the spread of the disease. Malaria transmission can be reduced by preventing mosquito bites by distribution of inexpensive mosquito nets and insect repellents, or by mosquito-control measures such as spraying insecticides inside houses and draining standing water where mosquitoes lay their eggs (Kilama and Ntouni, 2009). Mosquito nets help keep mosquitoes away from people and greatly reduce the infection and transmission of malaria (WHO, 2004). However, the inexpensive mosquito nets are not a perfect barrier. Insecticides Treated Nets (ITNs) have been shown to be the most cost-effective prevention method against malaria and are part of WHO's Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), but less than 2% of children in urban areas in Sub-Saharan Africa are protected by ITNs and this process poses a significant logistical problem in rural environment (Hawley, 2003, VOA News, 2004).

Environmental planning is another potent method of dealing with malaria incidence. Environment is largely determined by cultural, socio-economic and ecological factors (Olokesusi, 1991). Thus, environmental stressors and supporters work synergistically to provide the necessary resistance to unclean environment and disease. The environment dictates the incidence and prevalence of diseases all over the world and if timely action is not taken, it may lead to infection. The action may involve proper planning of the environment. Hall (1974) described planning as "an ordered sequence of operations, designed to lead to the achievement of either

a single or to a balance between several goals". John Glasson (1974) defined planning as "a future-oriented, problem-solving process". That is, a sequence of actions designed to solve current and anticipated problems resulting from the use or misuse of the land, location of activities, movement of people and goods, and careless management of the environment (Adedipe, 2002). It should be noted that the environment is retaliatory and the wrong use of the environment may have adverse consequences on the health conditions of the people, whose interest planning is trying to protect. Hence, planning the environment will be a good way of eradicating malaria incidence by disabling the chances of mosquito to breed.

Mosquitoes may be controlled by eliminating their breeding places or by spraying these places with oil or insecticides (Redmond, 2009). For maximum protection against malaria, therefore, efforts to eradicate malaria by eliminating mosquitoes must be a success in Nigeria. Malaria has implications on poverty, the economy development, in rural areas, on public expenditure, and currently serves as the greatest disease and health burden in Africa in particular and developing countries in general. However in Nigeria, the control of the disease is still not visible and very difficult.

The study aimed at applying multi-linear regression method to analyse the socio-economic factors associated with malaria incidence among various socio-economic household in rural areas. The objective of the paper is to examining whether any relationship exists between malaria incidence and socio-economic characteristics of the total number of members in a household in rural areas. The research hypothesis states that there is significant relationship between socio-economic characteristics and rate of malaria incidence of the total number of members in a household in rural areas.

The Study Area

Akinyele local government area lies between latitude $7^{\circ} 29'$ to $7^{\circ} 40'$ while its longitude ranges from $3^{\circ} 45'$ to $4^{\circ} 04'$. The total land area is about 219.2km^2 . It is located along the northern area of Ibadan city. Further, the area is bounded in the north by Afijio local government area, in the west by Ido local government area, in the south by Ibadan north local government area and in the east by Lagelu local government area and Osun State. The local government is divided into 12 electoral (political) wards, namely Ikereku (Ward 1), Labode/Oboda/Olanla (Ward 2), Arulogun (Ward 3), Onidundu/ Amosun (Ward 4), Moniya (Ward 5), Akinyele (Ward 6), Iwokoto/Amosun (Ward 7). Others are Ojoo/Ajibode/Orogun/Owe/Kankon (Ward 8), Ijaye (Ward 9), Alabata (Ward 10), Okegbemi/Mele (Ward 11) and Iroko (Ward 12).

The study area experiences a tropical type of climate. Akinyele Local Government recorded a mean annual temperature of about 32°C . The relative humidity can be as high as 95% area and a total of about 1250 mm as mean annual rainfall. The area is located in the forest belt of the country, particularly in the tropical rain forest. The forest is not as extensive as it used to be in the area. It is now restricted to some parts, such as Ijaiye forests reserve, International Institute of Tropical Agricultural [IITA] forest reserve to mention but a few. Generally, the vegetation in the area is broadly dominated by palm trees and the area may be referred to as a "dry forest belt". The soil of the area were formed from rocks of pre-Cambrian basement complex formation particularly granites, gneisses, quartz-schist, biotite gneisses and schist. They were formed under moist semi-deciduous forest cover and belong to the major soil group called ferruginous tropical soil.

According to the 2006 census as released by the National Population Commission, the population of Akinyele local government was 211,359. The sex structure obtained revealed that there were more female than males but with a narrow difference of 435 in their figures.

Another salient feature of the population is the predominance of Yoruba ethnic group, which is over 95% of the total population of the area. Other notable ethnic groups are Hausa (reside mostly in Sasa), Igbo, Edo, Fulani, Nupe, Tivs, Efiks among others. The major occupation of the people is agriculture. This is because the area has a favourable climate and soil condition. Moreover, trading and civil service work are now competing with agriculture in the area. However, because the farmers also market their surplus agricultural products most markets in the area are periodic.

Data and Method

The source of data for this work relies on both primary and secondary sources of data.

The secondary data for this study were obtained from internet sources, library books, theses, dissertations, and books, planning journals, magazines, seminar papers, newspapers and other publications relevant to the topic. Other secondary information collected include a map of Nigeria showing Oyo State (Fig. I), a map of Oyo State showing all 33 local government areas (Fig. II) and a map of Akinyele Local Government Area showing the location of all the 12 wards and the villages (Fig. III); a list of the major rural settlements, number of health facilities and the estimated population (1996) of the local government areas from the Health Unit of the Local government council and National Population Census respectively.

Table 1.1: Number of Estimated Households, Number of Selected Households In each of the Wards in Akinyele Local Government

Ward/Name	Number of Estimated Buildings	Number of Households Selected	Percentage of selected households
1 (Ikereku)	219	7	1.8
2 (Labode/Oboda/Olanla)	1039	31	8.0
3 (Arulogun)	936	28	7.2
4 (Onidundu/ Amosun)	159	5	1.3
5 (Moniya)	2595	78	20.2
6 (Akinyele)	745	22	5.7
7 (Iwokoto/Amosun)	586	18	4.7
8 (Ojoo/Ajibode/Orogun/Owe/Kankon)	4614	138	35.7
9 (Ijaye)	841	25	6.5
10 (Alabata)	255	8	2.1
11 (Okegbemi/Mele)	115	3	0.8
12 (Iroko)	797	24	6.2
Total	12,901	387	100

Source: Authors' Field Survey, July/August, 2011.

A reconnaissance survey of the study area was conducted with a view to familiarizing the author with all the identified major rural settlements and the number of buildings in the local government based on the Base Maps collected from the Town Planning Unit of the local government. The author did all that with the help of some research assistants. Questionnaire was designed to reflect the aim and objectives of the study. The set of questionnaire was directed to members of household. Data on the age, marital status, and number of children, religion and the level of education of the respondents were obtained. Some other information obtained were level of income, occupation and number of years lived in the village.

Sampling and Procedures

In this study household was the basic unit of sampling. In order to ensure an equal and a fair representation, total number of property was used to select sample with the belief that there will be at least one household in each property. Three per cent (387) of the entire property (12,901) in the local government were selected. The three per cent of the properties were then proportionally selected from each of the wards through simple random (lucky dip) and systematic sampling methods for investigation. The number of buildings selected is: seven in ward 1, 31 in ward 2, 28 in ward 3, 5 in ward 4, 78 in ward 5, 22 in ward 6, 18 in ward 7, 138 in ward 8, 25 in ward 9, 8 in ward 10, 3 in ward 11 and 24 in ward 12 (Table 1.1). From each of these buildings, one member was then interviewed (Table 1.2). As showed in Table 1.2, the entire sets of questionnaire distributed were retrieved.

The twelve wards and the three per cent of the households selected would be representative enough because there are broad similarities among the customs and cultures of the people in the region and malaria is not linguistic bias. Systematic and Simple random sampling technique (lucky dip/blind dip method) were applied to select the buildings and households investigated so as to eliminate biases.

Table 2: Number of Estimated Properties, Households Selected, Questionnaire Distributed and Retrieved

Wards	Number Of Buildings	Number Of Buildings Selected	% of Buildings Selected	Number Of Questionnaire Distributed	Number Of Questionnaire Retrieved	% Of Questionnaire Retrieved in each ward
1	219	7	2	7	7	100
2	1039	31	8	31	31	100
3	936	28	7	28	28	100
4	159	5	1	5	5	100
5	2595	78	20	78	78	100
6	745	22	6	22	22	100
7	586	18	5	18	18	100
8	4614	138	36	138	138	100
9	841	25	6	25	25	100
10	255	8	2	8	8	100
11	115	3	1	3	3	100
12	797	24	6	24	24	100
Total	12,901	387	100	387	387	

Source: Authors' Field Survey, July/August, 2011.

Household Sampling

Since the major occupation of the majority of the people in the local government is farming, it was very difficult to meet them (especially men) at home both in the morning and the afternoon. The survey was, therefore, done during the periodic market of the selected villages and in places of work of the respondents. On getting to a particular building for survey, the head of the household was interviewed. Those that could not be seen at home were sought for in their work places including the market. This was done to enhance the quality of the information. Other criteria used in the selection of the respondents within the household were, especially, if the head of the household could not be found were: The respondents must be residing in the village more than a year before the study; and the respondents must be married or above 18 years or must have had a child.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis was applied to analyze the data collected. The results were then used to determine the relationship between the malaria incidence and the total number of members in a household in the study area.

Data Collection Instrument (Schedule) and the Administration of Data Collection Schedule

The main instrument of this study was some sets of questionnaire. The author administered the questionnaire together with some trained students of the department of the Urban and Regional Planning, the Polytechnic, Ibadan. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis was applied to analyze the data collected. The study did not include the etymological study of the disease and the vector. The surveys conducted in this study were self-reports. It was assumed that these self-report were unbiased and accurate.

ANALYSIS, RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Social -Economic Characteristics of the Respondents

The social and economic characteristics includes the age distribution, gender status, marital status, household size, religion affiliation, educational status, level of income and occupational characteristics, among others, of the respondents.

Age Distribution of the Respondents

The result in Table 3.1 shows that 4.1% of the respondents are below 18 years as 0.5% of the respondents are above 57 years. From a total percentage of adults (respondents above 18) that accounted for 95.9%, more than 94% are within the working ages of between 18 and 57. It should be noted that the 4.1% of the respondents that are below 18 years were married with children. This implies that the population of the study area is made up of people in their prime age.

Table 3.1: The Age Distribution of the Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 18	16	4.1
18-25	50	12.9
26-33	42	10.9
34-41	121	31.1
42-49	134	34.6
50-57	22	5.7
Above 57	2	0.5
Total	387	100.0

Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

Genders of the Respondents

The result in Table 3.2 indicates that females accounted for 57.6% of the total respondents, while males makeup of 42.4%. The higher percentage of the female respondents is attributed to the non availability of the male heads of the household during the time of survey because of their major occupation, which is farming, that demands that they leave home very early and come back very lately.

Table 3.2: Gender Status of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Male	164	42.4
Female	223	57.6
Total	387	100.0

Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

Marital Status of the Respondents

Some percentages of the respondents are widowed, divorced, separated or never married. The result in Table 3.3 shows that over 66 % of the respondents are married while 18.9% of them are singles. A close observation of the Table (3.3) shows that almost all categories of people were interviewed. It should be noted that 'Never Married' in the Table does not mean that they were children below 18 years of age, but single families. It could be

concluded that the more than 66% that are married indicates growing population, hence the need for proper management of health infrastructural facilities to meet up the anticipated population and rural growth.

Table 3.3: Marital status of the respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Single Mother	73	18.9
Married	258	66.7
Widowed	30	7.8
Divorced	17	4.4
Separated	5	1.3
Never married	4	1.0
Total	387	100.0

Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

Households Size of the Respondents

Household size refers to the total number of persons living together as a family unit sharing basic facilities such as shelter, kitchen and so on (Ohwofasa, 2010). It should be noted that most of the respondents considered it as a taboo to give the actual number of persons within their families, especially the number of children, and therefore the household size here should be assumed to be accurate.

Table 3.4: Household Size of the Respondents

Household size	Frequency	%
1	14	3.6
2	19	4.9
3	31	8.0
4	67	17.3
5	84	21.7
6	117	30.2
7	51	13.2
8 and above	4	1.0
Total	387	100

Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

Result in Table 3.4 shows those respondents who claimed that they were with no child, wife or husband account for 3.6% and those with between 2 and 3 members account for 12.9% while 39.0% of the respondents have between 4 and 5 members. Some 44.4% of the respondents have six or more members. It could be inferred that not all respondents interviewed were with children but over 18 years old.

The result in Table 3.4.1 shows the relationship between the household sizes and the number of malaria incidence of the respondents in 2010. It should be noted from the survey that, of the total number of household size of one in each count, only 6.3%, 3.9%, 1.8% and 7.7% had malaria episodes once, twice, three times and six times respectively in 2010. Of significance is that every member (100%) of household sizes of six and eight had malaria episodes twelve and eight times respectively in 2010. It could be inferred from the result in Table 3.4.1 that household sizes may have effect on the number of times of occurrences of malaria in an area.

Table 3.4.1: Cross tabulation of Household Size of the Respondents and the Number of Times of Malaria Episode in 2010

How many times did you have malaria in 2010 ? * House hold size Crosstabulation

			House hold size							Total	
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7		8 and above
How many times did you have malaria in 2010 ?	1	Count	5	4	9	17	12	26	7	0	80
		% within How many times did you have malaria in 2010 ?	6.3%	5.0%	11.3%	21.3%	15.0%	32.5%	8.8%	.0%	100.0%
	2	Count	7	11	14	24	39	55	28	0	178
		% within How many times did you have malaria in 2010 ?	3.9%	6.2%	7.9%	13.5%	21.9%	30.9%	15.7%	.0%	100.0%
	3	Count	1	2	7	9	11	12	11	2	55
		% within How many times did you have malaria in 2010 ?	1.8%	3.6%	12.7%	16.4%	20.0%	21.8%	20.0%	3.6%	100.0%
	4	Count	0	1	1	7	12	7	2	0	30
		% within How many times did you have malaria in 2010 ?	.0%	3.3%	3.3%	23.3%	40.0%	23.3%	6.7%	.0%	100.0%
	5	Count	0	0	0	6	5	10	1	0	22
		% within How many times did you have malaria in 2010 ?	.0%	.0%	.0%	27.3%	22.7%	45.5%	4.5%	.0%	100.0%
6	Count	1	1	0	2	3	6	0	0	13	
	% within How many times did you have malaria in 2010 ?	7.7%	7.7%	.0%	15.4%	23.1%	46.2%	.0%	.0%	100.0%	
7	Count	0	0	0	2	2	0	2	0	6	
	% within How many times did you have malaria in 2010 ?	.0%	.0%	.0%	33.3%	33.3%	.0%	33.3%	.0%	100.0%	
8.00	Count	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	
	% within How many times did you have malaria in 2010 ?	.0%	.0%	.0%	.0%	.0%	.0%	.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
12.00	Count	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	
	% within How many times did you have malaria in 2010 ?	.0%	.0%	.0%	.0%	.0%	100.0%	.0%	.0%	100.0%	
Total	Count	14	19	31	67	84	117	51	4	387	
	% within How many times did you have malaria in 2010 ?	3.6%	4.9%	8.0%	17.3%	21.7%	30.2%	13.2%	1.0%	100.0%	

Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

Educational Status

The result in Table 3.6 reveals that only 11.4% of the respondents have no formal education. It could be inferred from Table 3.6 that majority of the respondents are educated; respondents with no education or otherwise only accounted for 13.0%. Some 87.0% have up to primary formal education; it then means that "Roll Back Malaria" Campaign would be successful if the educated in the local government are made to be involved.

Table 3.6: Educational Status of the Respondents

Level of Education	Frequency	%
Non formal education	44	11.4
Primary	70	18.0
Secondary	100	25.8
Tertiary	167	43.2
Others (Specify)	6	1.6
Total	387	100

Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

Level of Income per Annum

Table 3.7: Level of Income of the Respondents

Level of income	Frequency	%
Less than 24000	146	37.7
25000-48000	111	28.7
49000-72000	66	17.1
72000-92000	25	6.5
More than 92000	39	10.1
Total	387	100

Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

Survey shows that only 10.1% of the respondents earned more than ₦ 920000 per annum but it is sufficed to note that the respondents always felt reluctant in disclosing their actual income (Table 3.7). More than 89% of the respondents, from Table 3.7, earned less than ₦8, 000.00 per month which have implication on level of expenditure on malaria preventive measures by the individual respondents. The variation in income was as a result of the variation in their occupation and status. The result in table 3.7 implies that the higher population is incapable of affording a good shelter, feeding, healthcare, and clothing, which are basic needs with resultant negative effect on the environment and human quality. This implies poor health and poor sanitation in the unplanned environment due to their low purchasing power.

Occupational Status

The result in Table 3.8 shows that a majority (37.2%) of the respondents were civil servants who were traced to their places of work from their respective homes and 24.5% accounts for the respondents that are traders. It should be noted that because the majority of the women in the rural areas do sell the family farm produce by themselves they therefore prefer calling themselves traders rather than farmers. The female counterpart, therefore, not only assists in land cultivation but also help in marketing the farm products. Majority of those who called themselves farmers are male respondents.

It should be noted that it is very hard to see somebody engaging in other profession without having personal farmland as his or her part-time occupation. Therefore, the claim that the major occupation of the people in the study area is agricultural activities is not a farce. Table 3.8 shows that no occupation is discriminated against and the decision arrived at concerning the campaign to eradicating malaria would be acceptable to the generality of the rural areas.

Table 3.8: Occupation of the Respondents

Level of income	Frequency	%
Trading	95	24.5
Farming	52	13.4
Artisan	31	8.0
Civil servant	144	37.2
Student/Apprentice	52	13.4
Unemployed	13	3.4
Total	387	100

Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

Distributional Pattern of Malaria Incidence

The result in Table 3.11 shows that 47.0% of the respondents had two members of the families with malaria episodes in 2010 and the families with not less than four members of malaria episodes accounted for 43.4%. About 7.0% had not less than 6 of their families and 8 members of 2.6% of the total number of the respondents had malaria in 2010. Relating the number of the family members that had malaria in 2010 with the political wards (Table 3.11.1) it would show that ward 2 had the greatest percentage (83.95%) of members of families with not less than two members and ward 4 had the lowest (20.0%). Ward 4 had the greatest percentage of 80.0% of the wards where not less than four of the family members had malaria episodes and ward 2 had the lowest cases of two members of the family. The data also shows that in wards 3 (3.6%), 5 (5.1), 6 (4.5%) and 8 (2.9%), not less than 8 members of the families had malaria episodes in 2010. This table confirms the endemic nature of the disease in the study area.

Table 3.11: Number of Members of family of Respondents with Malaria Episode in 2010

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
1-2	182	47.0
3-4	168	43.4
5-6	27	7.0
7-8	10	2.6
Above 8	0	0
Total	387	100

Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

Table 3.11.1: Number of family Members of Respondents with Malaria Episode in 2010 (Cross Tabulation)

Pölitical wards * How many members of your family had malaria in 2010 ? Crosstabulation

			How many members of your family had malaria in 2010 ?				Total
			1-2	3-4	5-6	7-8	
Pölitical wards	Ward 1	Count	2	5	0	0	7
		% within Pölitical wards	28.6%	71.4%	.0%	.0%	100.0%
	Ward 2	Count	26	5	0	0	31
		% within Pölitical wards	83.9%	16.1%	.0%	.0%	100.0%
	Ward 3	Count	12	13	2	1	28
		% within Pölitical wards	42.9%	46.4%	7.1%	3.6%	100.0%
	Ward 4	Count	1	4	0	0	5
		% within Pölitical wards	20.0%	80.0%	.0%	.0%	100.0%
	Ward 5	Count	30	33	11	4	78
		% within Pölitical wards	38.5%	42.3%	14.1%	5.1%	100.0%
	ward 6	Count	12	9	0	1	22
		% within Pölitical wards	54.5%	40.9%	.0%	4.5%	100.0%
	Ward 7	Count	10	7	1	0	18
		% within Pölitical wards	55.6%	38.9%	5.6%	.0%	100.0%
	ward 8	Count	62	61	11	4	138
		% within Pölitical wards	44.9%	44.2%	8.0%	2.9%	100.0%
	ward 9	Count	11	13	1	0	25
		% within Pölitical wards	44.0%	52.0%	4.0%	.0%	100.0%
	Ward 10	Count	3	5	0	0	8
		% within Pölitical wards	37.5%	62.5%	.0%	.0%	100.0%
	ward 11	Count	1	1	1	0	3
		% within Pölitical wards	33.3%	33.3%	33.3%	.0%	100.0%
	Ward 12	Count	12	12	0	0	24
		% within Pölitical wards	50.0%	50.0%	.0%	.0%	100.0%
Total		Count	182	168	27	10	387
		% within Pölitical wards	47.0%	43.4%	7.0%	2.6%	100.0%

Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

The result in Table 3.11.1 also shows that there is spatial variation in the occurrences of malaria incidence, across the political wards within the study area, as typified by all the wards.

Stretching the analysis further, the hypothesis that states that there is significant relationship between malaria incidence and the socio-economic characteristics of the total number of members in a household that had malaria episode in 2010 was tested. The dependent variable is the number of members of the family that had the incidence of malaria in 2010 in the study area. The independent variables are the socio-economic characteristics of the members of the families which include the age, sex, education status etc etc.

A multiple linear regression analysis test was conducted as a statistical method to verify and ascertain the above mentioned hypothesis. The Statistical Package for Social Science was applied. The results are presented in Tables 4.5, 4.6, 4.7, and 4.8.

Table 4.5: Variable entered/Removed^b

Model	Variable Entered	Variable Removed	Method
1	House hold size, Education status, Gender, Religion, Age, Marital Status, Level of Income per Annum, Occupation		Enter

a. All requested variables entered.

b. Dependent variable: How many members of the family had malaria in 2010?

c. Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

Table 4.6: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error Of The Estimate
1	.258 ^a	.067	.047	.70611

- a. Predictor: Constant), Household size, Educational Status, Gender, Religion, Age, Marital Status, Level of Income per annum, Occupation
 b. Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

Table 4.7: ANOVA^b

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Significant
1 Regression	13.441	8	1.680	3.370	.001 ^a
Residual	188.466	378	.499		
Total	201.901	386			

Predictor: Constant), Household size, Educational Status, Gender, Religion, Age, Marital Status, Level of Income per annum, Occupation

Dependent variable: How many members of the family had malaria in 2010?

Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

Table 4.8: Regression Coefficients^a

Model	Un-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
	B	Std. error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.204	.277		4.345	.000
Age	-.039	.035	-.069	-1.108	.268
Gender	-.037	.074	-.025	-.503	.615
Marital status	.071	.051	.084	1.396	.164
Level of income per annum	.016	.033	.029	.490	.625
Occupation	-.008	.031	-.017	-.263	.793
Educational status	-.070	.047	-.103	-1.489	.137
Religion	.145	.061	.123	2.386	.018
Household size	.099	.025	.214	4.019	.000

Dependent variable: How many members of the family had malaria in 2010?

Source: Authors' Field Survey, June/July, 2011.

The result in Table 4.6 shows that the correlation coefficient (R) is 0.258, significant at P=0.001, which shows positive correlation between dependent variable (the number of members of the family that had malaria in 2010) and independent variables (Age, Gender, Marital status, Level of income per annum, Occupation, Educational status, Religion and Household size of the respondents). R² which is coefficient of determination is 0.067, when multiply by 100 it is equal to 6.7% (0.067x100%), which implies that about 6.7% of the incidence of malaria in aggregate life of members in the households (*the number of members of the family that had malaria in 2010*) is explained by the socio-economic factors such as age of the respondents, gender, marital status, level of income per annum, occupation, educational status, religion and the household size. Other factors which are not considered in this study account for the remaining 93.3%. Such factors may include culture and custom, health habit, environmental sanitation, belief system etc. The result in Table 4.7 also shows that the calculated F-value is 3.370 and this is related to the P-value or the significance value that is 0.001.

Significantly, the table of coefficient (Table 4.8) shows that the most significant factors influencing malaria incidence is household size, $\beta=0.214$ at p=0.000. The implication of this is that as the household size increases, likewise the cases or malaria incidence increases. Therefore, intensifying family planning campaign and awareness is a much needed task towards efforts at reducing malaria incidence. This is because the lesser the family size, the greater the capability to cater for the family. This shows that household size is one important factor that cannot be downplay when dealing with health of people.

Ohwofasa, (2010) refers to a household as the total numbers of persons living together as a family unit sharing basic facilities such as shelter, kitchen and so on. Simpson, (2008) sees a family as a basic social group united through bonds of kinship or marriage, present in all societies. The nuclear family—two adults and their children—is the main unit in some societies. In others, it is a subordinate part of an extended family, which also consists of grandparents and other relatives. A third family unit is the single-parent family, in which children live with an unmarried, divorced, or widowed mother or father.

Corbett (2008) have shown that people who grow up in persistently poor households experience more difficulties throughout their lives than those raised in households that are above the poverty level. It was admitted by Ettliling (1994), Humphreys (2001) and, Gallup and Sachs (2001) that poverty is both cause and effect of malaria disease and that malaria is not just a disease commonly associated with poverty but also a cause of poverty. It could be explained that the use of mosquito nets and other protective measures would be improve with the improvement in the socioeconomic status.

Religion and household size are highly interrelated, especially in the developing countries. Paden, (2008) sees religion as sacred engagement that is believed to be a spiritual reality. Some cultures recognize polygamy—that is, marriage to more than one wife or husband at a time. The marriage of one man to two or more women at the same time is called polygyny. Where polygamy exists, in almost all cases it means polygyny is practiced. The early Christians outlawed polygyny and the church officially rejected the practice of polygyny in 1890. Under Islamic law today, a man may legally have as many as four wives. Polygyny is also practiced in some African nations (Skolnick, 2008). It could be inferred from the analysed data that a religion or culture that allows polygyny would rather encourage large household size and therefore high population densities, with consequential effects on exposing to malaria carrying insects.

It could be inferred from the above contributions that malaria and poverty are intimately connected and the better-offs have improved case reporting and likely to seek treatment unlike the poor especially those in the rural areas of the developing countries who would not be able to afford protective measures or decent environment.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It is noted that in the poor and often rural areas household size is large, and sanitation is poor, contributing to the growing incidence of the disease. If any of these is lowered sufficiently, therefore, the parasite will sooner or later disappear from that area. From the data gathered and analyzed, majority of people in the study area are poor, with high family size and poor environmental sanitation.

Soap opera and staged play in local languages disseminating essential information about malaria to the people should be produced. Drama should be staged in strategic locations in rural areas teaching family planning and family health education. This would break the barrier surrounding ignorance of unhealthy living such as poor sanitation and large family size.

Films will be useful when communicating with illiterate and semi-illiterate audience. Film in the languages understood by the rural audience should be encouraged and made free-of-charge in the rural settlements. Consequent government policies and programmes towards achievement of goals and objectives of poverty reduction should take account of the interest of the rural dwellers.

For adequate provision of facilities and public utilities in urban and rural settlements to meet human needs and aspirations, and to ensure orderly arrangement of land uses so as to provide habitable and decent forum for the efficient performance of human activities, planning is needed (Onibokun, 1984)

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